

“Baseline Report on Industry-Academia Co-creation Approaches”

DELIVERABLE

Version 2.0

D1.1

05 2024

Project Number: 101070297

Project Acronym: INDUSAC

Project title: Quick Challenge-driven, Human-centered Co-Creation mechanism for INDUStry-Academia Collaborations

Starting date: 01/09/2022

Duration in months: 36

Call (part) identifier: HORIZON-CL4-2021-HUMAN-01

Topic: HORIZON-CL4-2021-HUMAN-01-20

Technical reference

<i>Deliverable: 1.1</i>	
<i>Work Package:</i>	1
<i>Due Date:</i>	M4
<i>Submission Date:</i>	22/12/2022
<i>Resubmission Date (based on EC feedback)</i>	05/2024
<i>Start Date of Project:</i>	01/09/2022
<i>Duration of Project:</i>	36 months
<i>Organisation Responsible of Deliverable:</i>	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology
<i>Version:</i>	2.0
<i>Status:</i>	Final
<i>Author name(s):</i>	Imke Hellwig, Annika Bastian, Christoph Kempf, Katharina Dühr
<i>Reviewer(s):</i>	Steering Committee
<i>Type:</i>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Report <input type="checkbox"/> Other
<i>Dissemination level:</i>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> PU <input type="checkbox"/> SEN

History of Changes:

Date	Comments	Version
12 2022	<i>Version 1 submitted December 2022</i>	V1.0
05 2024	<i>Final Version</i>	V2.0

SUMMARY OF THE PROJECT

INDUSAC's main objective is to develop and validate a state-of-the-art, Industry Academia collaboration (IAC) mechanism for quick, challenge-driven, human-centred co-creation. Its aim is to build upon pre-existing IAC mechanisms such as EIT KICs and to facilitate a simple, user-friendly co-creation process that allows to develop solutions that clearly address the needs and interests of companies, students, and researchers in the EU, with special attention to widening and associated countries. Of a highly digitalised nature, our project pilots the mechanism's two main components: a methodology developed by applying human-centred design principles and an online platform aimed at connecting stakeholders from the industry-academia ecosystem and at supporting them throughout their co-creation journey.

The INDUSAC methodology provides the guidance and tools needed to power the process, whilst the platform stands as a networking space for stakeholders to connect, as well as a co-creation arena to develop joint solutions. Through the experience of supporting at least 300 transnational co-creation teams throughout project lifetime, the INDUSAC mechanism and its two key components will be successively improved until project end, delivering a tested mechanism ready for replication and upskilling. It is expected for INDUSAC to also create a dynamic community of industry-academia stakeholders, including at least 1000 companies, 3000 students and 300 researchers by project end. The INDUSAC counts with a strong interdisciplinary, cross-sectorial and geographically balanced partnership that counts with the needed expertise and network to achieve our project's goals.

ABSTRACT

This report D1.1: "Baseline Report on Industry-Academia Co-Creation Approaches" is part of Work Package (WP) 1: "Human-centred development of the INDUSAC co-creation methodology" of the project "Quick challenge-driven, human-centred co-creation mechanism for INDUSty-Academia collaborations" (INDUSAC).

D1.1 aims to provide a comprehensive overview of approaches to industry-academia collaboration (IAC) and to share new insights, focusing on the essential success factors for collaboration. First, the success factors for successful collaboration already identified in the literature are presented. In addition, best practice solutions on the market are also identified and introduced. Surveys and interviews provide further insights into motivation, processes, payment flows, success factors, and barriers of previous collaborations. All partners participated in conducting the interviews and surveys on both academic and industrial group. The detailed analysis and validation of the results revealed 22 essential success factors which are clustered into five groups: good communication and feedback, information and (technical) support, motivation and commitment, people and team, and structure and organization. Moreover, insights into motivation, structure, and barriers to an IAC were identified. The results obtained in this report will be used as input factors for the development of the methodology and the platform of the INDUSAC project.

LIST OF ACRONYMS

EU	European Union
FSTP	Financial Support for Third Parties
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IAC	Industry-Academia Collaboration
INDUSAC	Quick challenge-driven, human-centred co-creation mechanism for INDUSty-ACademia collaborations
NDA	Non-Disclosure Agreement
RQ	Research Question
SME	Small and Medium-sized Enterprises
WP	Work Package

TABLE OF CONTENTS

SUMMARY OF THE PROJECT	3
ABSTRACT	4
LIST OF ACRONYMS	5
I. INTRODUCTION	8
1. Overview of Task.....	8
2. Structure of the Baseline Report on Industry-Academia Co-creation Approaches.	8
II. DESKTOP RESEARCH – SUCCESS FACTORS IN IACS.....	9
1. Good Communication and Feedback	10
2. Information and (Technical) Support	11
3. Motivation and Commitment.....	11
4. People and Team.....	11
5. Structure and Organisation.....	12
III. REFERENCES: ONLINE INNOVATION PLATFORMS & CASCADE FUNDING.....	13
1. Agorize.....	13
2. Telanto.....	16
3. Summary of Online Innovation Platforms	19
4. Cascade Funding.....	19
IV. METHODOLOGY	22
1. Template for IACs Best-Practice Collection.....	22
2. Interview for Detailed IAC Insights	24
3. Survey to Support Interview Results	29
4. Focus Groups.....	30
V. PRESENTATION OF RESULTS.....	33
1. Participant Background	33
2. Collaboration Background.....	34
3. Collaboration Procedure	37
4. Success Factors and Barriers.....	37

5.	Results.....	43
6.	Conclusion – Thoughts of Participants.....	44
VI.	CONCLUSION.....	46
VII.	LIST OF REFERENCES.....	47
VIII.	ANNEXES.....	49
IX.	LIST OF FIGURES.....	53
X.	LIST OF TABLES.....	55

I. INTRODUCTION

1. Overview of Task

This report addresses the first objective of WP1 and forms the basis for the Industry-Academia Collaboration (IAC) approaches. It aims to identify the essential factors for IAC which will be used as input factors to develop the platform and the methodology. Therefore, the success factors for IACs are first identified through a literature review. By examining existing collaboration platforms, initial best practices and references for the platform are collected. Interviews and surveys are used to gain insights into the motivation, structure, and background of collaborations. A special focus is on the identification of essential success factors and barriers.

The methods were collected both on the side of academia (students and researchers) and the side of the industry. A total of 23 interviews and 71 surveys were conducted. The data was then analysed and success factors and barriers to collaboration were identified. The elaborated success factors were validated by four focus groups at different locations in the EU.

2. Structure of the Baseline Report on Industry-Academia Co-creation Approaches

The report consists of six key sections. The introduction provides a brief overview of the INDUSAC project and situates the baseline report within the project. Furthermore, the content and the goal of the Baseline report are presented. Section II Desktop research – success factors in IACs presents success factors in collaborations found in the literature. Section III presents and evaluates existing platforms for co-creation. The methodology used regarding the interview, survey, and focus groups is part of section IV, Methodology. Section V, Presentation of results presents and analyses in detail the findings obtained in the previous sections, focusing on the success factors. The last section (VI) Conclusion summarizes the report and the obtained findings. Figure 1 shows the six sections of the report.

Figure 1 : Structure of the baseline report

II. DESKTOP RESEARCH – SUCCESS FACTORS IN IACS

The following section addresses the success factors described in the literature for successful collaboration between industry and academia. The goal is to gain insight into previous research findings and provide a basis for later comparison with the factors identified in the survey and interviews.

The Scopus database was used to identify relevant literature which provides results on success factors in university-industry collaborations. The search term comprises the terms “industry-academia collaboration” and “university-industry collaboration”, which are often used interchangeably, and the terms “success” and “barrier”. In Figure 2, you can find the used search string.

Search string

```
TITLE-ABS-KEY(("Industry-Academia Collaboration*" or "University-Industry  
Collaboration*") AND ("Success*" or "Barrier*"))
```

Figure 2 : Used search string for the literature review

The 331 results found were further narrowed down based on the following criteria. The first criterium was that the literature is publicly available and in English. The number of publications has increased steadily since 2015, highlighting the growing relevance and interest in IACs (see Figure 3). To get as up-to-date an impression as possible, only publications between 2015 and 2022 were included in the research. The 87 papers remaining after filtering were screened based on their abstract as well as their conclusion and were reduced to 14, which are used for the following literature review.

The following five categories are used to structure the factors: good communication and feedback, information and (technical) support, motivation and commitment, people and team, as well as structure and organization. These were created to structure the factors identified in the interviews and survey which are described and analysed in section V. Presentation of results. The same categories are used in both sections to ensure compatibility between the results of section V and the desktop research.

Figure 3 : Number of publications per year found based on the search string

1. Good Communication and Feedback

Communication is an essential factor in IAC, which is also described by some as critical since miscommunication is an obstacle to collaboration (Kleiner-Schaefer & Schaefer, 2022; Polese et al., 2021). To establish communication as a success factor in a project, there should be an effective and regular exchange between all stakeholders (Garousi et al., 2017; Hanid et al., 2019; Serbezov et al., 2022). Meaning that all stakeholders are in contact with each other and regularly share information about the project and its progress. Salimi et al. (2016), therefore, noted that frequent face-to-face meetings are important as they lead to trust and facilitate knowledge transfer. In their research, Polese et al. (2021) found that digital technology promotes communication success by enabling real-time communication and working on projects remotely. It is necessary to communicate frequently and provide the participants with different channels for communication. Standardized and frequent communication is also essential to work toward the project goal and revise the status regularly. It ensures that the focus is on problem-solving (Marijan & Gotlieb, 2021).

Good communication also includes listening, explaining, and requesting feedback (Cirella & Murphy, 2022). Feedback is not only mentioned in Cirella and Murphy (2022) study, but Serbezov et al. (2022) also noted that a feedback mechanism can guide a project and ensure that all stakeholders are pulling together, activities remain relevant and lead to the project goal.

2. Information and (Technical) Support

Access to relevant information within the project is a factor that should be ensured. In this context, the transfer should take place from both groups. Therefore, willingness to share knowledge is very important and a motivator of IAC (Garnweidner-Holme et al., 2021).

One way of providing information can be ensured by good knowledge management, e.g., through workshops (Garousi et al., 2017; Garousi et al., 2019). However, digitization also facilitates the sharing of information within the IAC (Polese et al., 2021).

3. Motivation and Commitment

Motivation is a success factor in IAC that has also been highlighted in relevant research. Serbezov et al. (2022) identified student motivation as a vital factor for collaboration. However, the industry group has to be engaged with the project, too.

The hypothesis that industry partners are not as motivated as academic partners to participate in collaboration was disproved by the observations of Garousi et al. (2019). Their findings go even further and mention that the industry partner must be a champion. Indicating that for the success of the project, partners should not just be assigned to the project but should be passionate and drive the collaboration forward.

Salimi et al. (2016) particularly emphasize the enthusiasm of both parties during a collaboration. Lack of or declining motivation among project participants can be a critical barrier to collaboration and can significantly impair and disrupt it. Therefore, the engagement of all stakeholders is an important success factor as it contributes significantly to the success of the project goal (Hanid et al., 2019; Salimi et al., 2016).

4. People and Team

Essential components of collaboration are the factors that fall under the heading of *people and team*. Suitable staffing in both the academic and industrial group is a key factor for collaboration (Serbezov et al., 2022). In Hanid et al. (2019) research, having the right project participants is one of the most important outcomes for a successful IAC. Not only the team members and their skills are relevant, but also the team dynamics and the relationship between the participants play a major role in collaboration (Steinmo & Rasmussen, 2018). Working as a team and speaking the same language regarding the project positively impacts IAC (Garousi et al., 2019; Serbezov et al., 2022). In their research, Polese et al. (2021) noted the positive influence of trusting relationships and a sense of familiarity on the management of IAC. Moreover, respect and appreciation toward all participants are success factors for a good team.

Building personal and lasting relationships also emerged from studies of IAC success (Serbezov et al., 2022). Having a team member with prior experience in IAC has a positive impact on the project and collaboration as well (Salimi et al., 2016). A positive influence on IAC is trust regarding the project and its success. In some cases, it took time to build, but the

presence of trust is important. However, in some cases, collaborative agreements that were too long also weakened trust in each other and the project (Ehrismann & Patel, 2015; Garnweidner-Holme et al., 2021).

Lack of qualifications on the part of the students and no good teamwork in both groups were mentioned as the main obstacles within the IAC (Fernandes et al., 2022; Serbezov et al., 2022).

5. Structure and Organisation

The success of collaborations is also influenced by factors concerning the structure and organization of a project. During the project development phase, it is crucial to write a clearly defined collaboration agreement that specifies who owns the collaboration results (Garnweidner-Holme et al., 2021). Thereby it is ensured that all participants share the same expectations of the project (Ehrismann & Patel, 2015). In particular, a clear definition of the goal, the milestones included, and the work packages are important for the success of an IAC (Hanid et al., 2019; Polese et al., 2021; Serbezov et al., 2022). Therefore, the project's success should be defined in advance and measurable (Garousi et al., 2019; Serbezov et al., 2022). In their research, Kauppila et al. (2015) emphasize the importance of transparent processes and a defined strategy for collaboration. To ensure that all participants know their roles, clear responsibilities must be defined. A project manager who is responsible for the schedule and deliverables and actively engages participants in the project to ensure success is also essential (Serbezov et al., 2022).

The project should use a platform where participants can communicate and share documents to facilitate collaboration. This way, barriers encountered during co-creation can be reduced, and the co-creation process can be enabled despite geographical distance (Polese et al., 2021).

Garousi et al. (2019), on the other hand, mention the importance of on-site collaboration in their research, partly due to sensitive company data.

Some studies have also identified funding as a success factor for collaboration. It acts as a motivator, especially for researchers, and is usually provided by the corporate group (Hanid et al., 2019; Serbezov et al., 2022).

The desktop research on success factors for IACs revealed that there are already several publications that address the key success factors and highlight their importance.

III. REFERENCES: ONLINE INNOVATION PLATFORMS & CASCADE FUNDING

In this section, two platforms that enable industry-academia collaborations are presented. In particular, the services and functionalities they offer are analysed. The goal is to get an impression of the platforms available on the market and to learn from best practices. The findings serve as a first reference and help in the development of the INDUSAC platform. Moreover, best practices regarding cascade funding will be presented.

Since INDUSAC is intended to be a European collaboration platform, platforms that offer opportunities for international IACs were selected as references. Agorize and Telanto are two platforms that already offer this on the market and are therefore presented in more detail below.

1. Agorize

Agorize is an open innovation platform where companies can publish challenges for students, start-ups, or developers. However, it can also be used for internal company challenges. The published challenges are only accessible to employees, who can then apply and solve the task alone or in teams. The platform was founded in 2011 and has already over five million registered users, including 1,700 universities, three million students, 300,000 start-ups, and 600,000 IT developers. Furthermore, well-known companies such as Amazon Web Services, Accenture, TotalEnergies, and L'Oréal are among the platform's users. Figure 4 shows some examples of challenges.

The screenshot displays the Agorize platform interface. At the top, there are navigation tabs: "All programs", "Startups challenges", "Students challenges", "Online hackathons", "Professional opportunities", and "Ecosystem opportunities". Below the tabs is a search bar. The main content area is titled "Open for registration" and features three challenge cards:

- Healthcare Startup Search** by VentureBlick: "Global search for healthcare startups that are 'Most Endorsed by the Medical Community'. Apply in your preferred language: English, 中文, 한국어". Eligibility: Start-up. Funding: Stand the chance to raise USD\$200,000 up to US\$5M in funding and win U... 37 Days left.
- Global Change Award 2023** by H&M Foundation: "H&M Foundation is looking for ideas and innovators to join the Global Change Award 2023 to create a more sustainable fashion and textile industry." Eligibility: Student, Start-up. Funding: Grant of 1 million euros, Access to 1-year tailor-made GCA Impact Acce... 11 Days left.
- NEC Innovation Challenge** by NEC: "Deliver the solutions of tomorrow – NEC is looking for startups with Healthcare & Life Science, Metaverse and Carbon neutral solutions to collaborate together!" Eligibility: Start-up. Funding: Total funding of up to US\$20,000, full proof of concept, support to en... 7 Days left.

Figure 4 : Agorize - list of open challenges (Agorize, 2022b)

Companies can publish challenges after inserting information about the task, schedule, selection process, and rewards on the landing page. The platform user and non-registered persons have access to all published tasks and their descriptions (Figure 5). Interested and registered persons can apply individually or in teams, depending on the task. The possibility of contacting other people and forming teams is also given. No regulations regarding team composition are given.

Agorize has many built-in software features that facilitate the co-creation process for companies and participants. For good communication, they offer a chat and webinar feature, as well as the ability to share and save files. No other tool is needed for data storage and organization. There is also the possibility of getting in touch with project participants at any time. Individual Gamification, interactive voting, and selection processes, and mentoring by experts are designed to increase participant engagement.

Figure 5 : Agorize - full information about the challenge (Agorize, 2022b)

As data and measurable facts are becoming increasingly important in today's world, Agorize provides companies with many insights, such as the communication success of the challenge (Figure 6). In addition, the platform can be connected to compatible company tools via interfaces. Participant information, project files, and results can be downloaded anytime.

Figure 6 : Agorize - company monitoring dashboard (Agorize, 2022a)

All in all, Agorize is a global platform that allows companies to publish challenges of any size not only for students, start-ups, and their employees. Due to their many years of experience, they already have a large network and are continuously adapting their offering. Data protection is guaranteed by the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) of the European Union (EU). Pricing for Agonize can be found on the company's website. The smallest version with 20 participants and one power user of the company is available as a free trial. The next higher package (20 participants and 3 power users) is available for 70€/month. But there are also packages with 1,000 participants and 20 power users for 1230€/month as well as customizable solutions. The costs must be paid by the companies (Agorize, 2022a).

2. Telanto

Telanto is a platform that supports and facilitates global collaboration between industry and academia (students and researchers).

Industry partners can use Telanto's templates to create assignments and publish them on the marketplace (Figure 7). Furthermore, they can respond to professors' calls for tenders. The same applies vice versa for the professors. Collaborations can only arise when industry and professors come into contact. Students do not have the opportunity to apply for open challenges in the marketplace themselves. In the marketplace, both parties can exchange ideas and agree on matching to start their collaboration. According to Telanto, the matching rate is almost 96%. After a successful match, partners can collaborate and develop solutions to individual challenges. Telanto supports them with its collaborative workspace, where participants have an overview of all challenges, relevant data, deadlines, and the status quo. In addition, chat and video capabilities enable exchange among and between parties. After completion of the project, the companies can evaluate the solutions and the student's skills. The students receive a certificate.

Figure 7 : Telanto - challenge building (Telanto, 2022)

Through Telanto collaboration (Figure 8), students can improve their skills and competencies, build a network with industry partners, and gain their first practical experience. The opportunity to enter long-term collaborations and offer practical courses are positive reasons for professors to join an IAC. For companies, collaboration can be the source of digital transformation and innovation. In addition, there is the possibility of talent acquisition.

Figure 8 : Telanto - collaboration space (Telanto, 2022)

Telanto is a complete solution that facilitates the process of collaboration between industry and universities. However, only professors and company representatives can engage in a new challenge. Students do not have the opportunity to search for new challenges themselves. In addition, the teams are not mixed, as the participants are students from the same university. References on the website of e. g. Intel or ZEISS show that well-known companies have used Telanto for the IAC. Information regarding costs could not be found on the website (Telanto, 2022).

3. Summary of Online Innovation Platforms

The following Table 1 provides an overview of the services offered by the Agorize and Telanto platforms presented in the previous sections.

Table 1 : Overview of innovation platforms

		Agorize	Telanto
Challenge publication	Challenge publication by the industry for students	●	●
	Challenge publication by the industry for others (start-ups, developers, own company)	●	○
	Call for challenges from academia	○	●
Collaboration type	industry - students	●	●
	industry - researchers	●	●
	industry - others	●	○
Application	Application by students without the support of the university	●	○
	Individual participation	●	○
	Team application with knowns (e.g. fellow students)	●	●
	Team application with unknowns	●	○
Collaboration support	Information and tips on collaboration	●	●
	Methodology	○	●
Features	Chat and video function	●	●
	Data storage and exchange	●	●
	KPI monitoring	●	○
Reward	Certificate	○	●
	Reward (money, mentoring, internship, etc.)	●	○

Legend

- included
- not included/no information

4. Cascade Funding

Cascade funding, also known as Financial Support for Third Parties (FSTP), is a commission mechanism to distribute public funding in order to assist beneficiaries, such as start-ups, scale-ups, Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SME), and/or mid-caps.

FSTP are open calls run by individual EU projects funded under Horizon Europe. Money is hence “cascaded” from the European Commission to the project and then to successful participants in the open call. Often also called Financial Support to Third Parties; third party is the legal definition of applicants in this case. Third parties receiving cascade funding under Horizon Europe, have a contract with the consortium of the EU-funded project of which they become a third party. This means that this consortium is liable to the European Commission for the third parties to which it provides financial support and, hence, no legal

and financial validation is necessary for these third parties, which makes quicker/easier for projects to have open calls in their projects.

- Why cascade?
 - Horizon Europe is difficult to access for SME, early career researchers, and other beneficiaries
 - Consortia that want to reach out and involve new actors in their research and innovation process
 - Lots of SMEs/start-ups/idea givers etc in a given technological community
- These open calls from EU-funded projects are usually competitive, have a European dimension and aim at:
 - Selecting tech start-ups or scale-ups for acceleration or incubation purposes (usually equity free),
 - Supporting pilots, demonstrations and/or experiments on a specific innovative technology or framework (usually with the participation of start-ups or SME), or
 - Integrating more participants to the project to extend its scope or to address specific tasks
- List of FSTP calls: <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/competitive-calls>
- Examples of projects that offered cascade funding: [KET4CP](#), [AMULET](#), [EIT Urban Mobility](#)

Figure 9 and Figure 10 show the advantages and challenges of cascade funding.

Advantages of cascade funding

- Application is much simpler and shorter
- Success rates are often higher
- Much shorter time to grant ~2 months
- Shorter term projects
- No need for 3 country participation
- Although funding is typically smaller

Figure 9 : Advantages of cascade funding

Challenges of cascade funding

- No direct or limited access of professional research organisations (via subcontracting) to funding unless they're members of project Consortium.
- Topics, target applicants, application processes and rules for participation are set by the project – there's no 'one size fits all' rule for cascade funding, it depends on the project.
- Lots of projects running.
- They are often hard to find.

Figure 10 : Challenges of cascade funding

IV. METHODOLOGY

The goal of this report is to provide a holistic view of IACs and highlight all the important and necessary factors that are needed to build the methodology and platform for a successful IAC. To achieve this goal, the following research questions (RQ) will be answered:

RQ1: What are the essential success factors in IACs?

RQ2: What are the challenges and barriers in IACs?

This section presents the methods used to answer the research question (see Figure 11). First, a template was created to gain insights into the partners' past IACs. These findings were considered input factors in creating the interview. Based on the interview guide, the survey was created. And as the last step, the four focus groups were planned.

Figure 11 : Overview of the methodology

1. Template for IACs Best-Practice Collection

To gather first experience values in industry-academia collaborations, a template (see Figure 12) was designed.

All partners of the INDUSAC project were asked to fill out the template for two of their past experiences in IACs. The knowledge gained helped to obtain first insights into previous collaborations. The answers to the template were used as input factors in the conceptualization of the interview and survey that will be introduced in the following sections:

1.1. Name

The first section asked for the individual's name, occupation, and project that his/her experience is related to. Since the INDUSAC project includes industry and university groups, this section provided insights into the project participants involved.

1.2. Project description

This section aimed to get more detailed information about the topic, goals, and results of the collaboration in which the project partners participated.

Name Name of contact person and project		Your profession <input type="checkbox"/> Industry <input type="checkbox"/> Researcher <input type="checkbox"/> Student	Involved stakeholders <input type="checkbox"/> Industry <input type="checkbox"/> Researcher <input type="checkbox"/> Student
Project description What was the project about? What was the result? 			
Incentives What was the motivation of each stakeholder for the collaboration? 			
Type of support What kind of support was required? (technical, personnel, etc.) 			
Time frame How long and intensive was the collaboration? 			
Barriers What barriers have been faced during the cooperation? 			
Legal and administrative points of attention What were the legal and administrative aspects of cooperation? 			
Cash Flow How was the cash flow during the collaboration? 			
Others Do you have any other remarks? 			

Figure 12 : Template

1.3. Incentives

Since project participants belong to different groups (industry, researcher, or student), they also have different motivations for participating in the IAC. This category provides information about the respective reasons for participation.

1.4. Type of support

Co-creation projects are all different because each company has specific needs that need to be met. This section is about the requested support in the collaboration (technical, personnel, etc.).

1.5. Time frame

Since INDUSAC plans to offer challenges with a duration of 4-8 weeks, the time frame and intensity of past experiences are also relevant factors this section generated insights about.

1.6. Barriers

When working together, barriers also arise from time to time which hinders work or processes. This section is created to obtain an initial overview of disruptions that have occurred in past collaborations.

1.7. Success factors

The presence of certain factors is necessary for successful collaboration. This category is used to find out which success factors contribute significantly to the success of a project.

1.8. Legal and administrative points

In the case of collaboration between different parties, who may also be located in various countries, the issue of confidentiality and data protection must often be taken into account. Experiences concerning anything related to legal or administrative best practices can be mentioned in this section.

1.9. Cash flow

This field gains insight into previous cash flows between the different parties within a collaboration.

1.10. Others

This field provides space for further notes and comments on the topic of collaboration that have not yet been expressed.

2. Interview for Detailed IAC Insights

In order to gain detailed insights into the different perspectives of students, researchers, and companies on IACs an interview guide was designed. To get as meaningful an

impression as possible, at least ten interviews were to be conducted with companies and at least ten interviews with academia (researchers or students). All partners helped to conduct the interviews.

2.1. Creation of the Interview Guide

To ensure the interviewer some freedom and a smooth flow of conversation the interview is semi-structured with no fixed order of open questions. This gives the interviewee a greater leeway, whereby the importance of individual points can be expressed, which can also lead to completely new insights.

The guide consists of three parts: introduction, main section, and conclusion as seen in Figure 13. In the introduction, the interviewer introduces shortly himself, the INDUSAC project, and the structure of the interview.

The main section consists of all relevant questions and is divided into six subsections which cover all phases of the collaboration from the interviewee's background, the collaboration procedure, and success factors to the result. For the development of this section and its questions, the findings from the template were used (see section IV.1). The last section completes the interview by giving the interviewee the chance to address open points and explain the further use of the interview results.

Figure 13 : Interview structure

The complete interview, which consists of about 20 questions, can be found on the following pages. Although the interview was conducted for both groups, the interview guide (cf. Figure 14) is identical, apart from two additional questions for the students regarding their motivation and learning.

Feedback was obtained from all partners before distributing the final version of the interview guide.

Interview guide

Introduction

- Thanks for the willingness to participate
- Short introduction of the interviewer
- Brief introduction of the INDUSAC project
- Goal of the interview:
 - Insights into the collaboration between academia and industry partners in order to identify success factors
 - Interview of both sides: industry and academia
- Description of the rough interview procedure
 - Approx. 20 questions
 - Duration: approx. 1h
- Recording of the interview
 - Reason: No loss of information and more fluent conversation due to the omission of notetaking.
 - Have privacy statement signed/verify that privacy statement is in place
- Clarification of open questions of the interview partner

Main section

Section 1: Background of the interview partner

- Please briefly introduce yourself.
 - Where are you currently employed? (Academia or industry)
 - In what position are you employed there? / What are you studying?
 - How long have you worked in the position?
 - What are your areas of expertise?

Section 2: Collaboration background

- Please tell about an industry academia collaboration that you have been involved in.
 - What was the goal of the collaboration?
 - Which stakeholders were involved?
 - What was the motivation of the collaboration for each stakeholder?
 - How did the collaboration come about? (Tender, EU project, etc.)
 - How did you end up on the project?
 - How long was the collaboration scheduled?
 - How large was the project team?
 - What kind of support was required (from academia, industry, funding body)?
- Especially for students:
 - What was/ What would be the motivation for you to participate in an industry-academia collaboration?

Figure 14 : Interview guide

Section 1: Background of the interview partner

- Please briefly introduce yourself.
 - Where are you currently employed? (Academia or industry)
 - In what position are you employed there? / What are you studying?

- How long have you worked in the position?
- What are your areas of expertise?

Section 2: Collaboration background

- Please tell about an industry-academia collaboration that you have been involved in.
 - What was the goal of the collaboration?
 - Which stakeholders were involved?
 - What was the motivation for the collaboration for each stakeholder?
 - How did the collaboration come about? (Tender, EU project, etc.)
 - How did you end up on the project?
 - How long was the collaboration scheduled?
 - How large was the project team?
 - What kind of support was required (from academia, industry, funding body)?
- Especially for students:
 - What was/ What would be the motivation for you to participate in an industry-academia collaboration?
 - What have you learned/ What do you hope to learn from a collaboration with industry partners?
- What have been the cash flows in the project?
 - Who were the funders?
 - What was the value?
 - Was there federal or EU funding and what was the funding rate?

Section 3: Collaboration procedure

- How did the collaboration take place?
 - What form of collaboration was used? (Independent work packages, collaborative content development, remote, present, or hybrid).
 - Which stakeholder provided which input?
 - How frequently did exchanges take place? (e.g., weekly regular meetings)

Section 4: Success factors and barriers to collaboration?

- What were the success factors of the collaboration?

- What went particularly well during the collaboration?
- What were external success factors? (e.g., legal)
- What were the internal success factors? (e.g., communication)
- What problems/barriers were encountered during the collaboration?
 - Were there any disruptive factors/barriers?
 - Which ones?
 - Were there administrative or legal barriers that needed to be addressed during the collaboration?
 - How did you resolve them?
 - What did you learn from them?

Section 5: Result

- How would you evaluate the output of the project?
 - Was it possible to achieve the project goal?
 - How were the results further used?

Section 6: Conclusion

- What general added value/what advantages do you hope to gain from cooperation with academia/industry?
- Would you enter cooperation with academia/industry again?
 - If yes: why?
 - If no: why not?
- What would you do differently in a new collaboration?
 - What would an optimal collaboration look like for you?
 - What basic requirements/success factors must be in place for this to happen?
- Are there any other collaborations with industry/academia planned?
 - Can you tell a bit about the project?
 - Could you imagine using INDUSAC in the collaboration?

2.2. Conduction of the Interviews

To generate a broad European view on IAC, the interviews were conducted with help of all partners of the INDUSAC project in the first two weeks of November. The partners were

completely free in choosing their interviewees besides the fact that they should have first touchpoints in IACs. The partners were split into two groups for conducting the interviews. One group conducted interviews with the academia group, and the other with the industry group. The classification can be seen in Table 2.

All interviews were conducted in English or at least the transcripts have been translated into English.

Table 2 : Overview of conducted interviews

Industry		Academia	
Partner	Number of interviews	Partner	Number of interviews
BAX	1	BAX	1
BIC	2	CIT UPC	3
CCIPB	3	CUT	1
CUT	1	Innoget	2
EITM	3	JSI	2
KIT	2	KIT	2
Sum	12	Sum	11

After conducting the interviews, partners sent the interview data consisting of a summary, the recording, and a consent form to KIT. With the help of an online tool, KIT transcribed all interviews. The process of the interview conduction can be seen in Figure 15.

Figure 15 : Conducting and evaluating the interviews

3. Survey to Support Interview Results

To validate the findings of the survey with quantitative statements a survey has been designed. For meaningful results, the survey should generate at least 50 results per group.

3.1. Creation of the Survey

As the survey shall support the results obtained in the interviews the questions are nearly the same and the survey consists of the same six sub-sections as the interview guide. The

survey does not only consist of open questions, various question types were used. In contrast to the interview, the survey's target group is persons with experience in IACs and without. However, important information is obtained on why people do or do not participate in IACs. Since some questions depend on the experience or profession of the participant, constraints have been set defining different scenarios for the proposed questions.

On the following page, you will find an overview of the content of the six sub-sections (see Figure 16). The survey consists of a total of 28 questions and the estimated time required to complete the survey was 20 to 30 minutes.

Figure 16 : Survey content

3.2. Conduction of the Survey

To comply with the requirements of the grant agreement and to create a European perspective, all partners were asked to share the survey in their network, with their contacts, or on social media. Publishing the survey was independent of whether the partners belonged to the industry or the academic group.

4. Focus Groups

The main objective of the focus groups was to validate the success factors identified in the surveys and interviews conducted. The idea was to organize four different focus groups in different geographical locations to assess if the experience of actors within that region was in line with the current results.

Bax & Company lead the preparation and execution of the focus groups. In terms of development and preparation, a very tight timeline had to be followed to guarantee sufficient input for these sessions from the surveys and interviews but also at the same time finalize the deliverable based on this input.

The four geographies selected were: Central EU, South-Eastern EU, Eastern EU, and Southern EU. For each of these areas, the members were invited by INDUSAC partners present in the region. On average, five to ten participants were present per session.

Two focus groups were organized on the 29th of November, one on the 30th of November, and one on the 1st of December. Each focus group lasted one hour, and the following agenda was used:

- 5' Welcome and Introduction: General introduction to INDUSAC and the session and its overall objectives
- 10' Tour de Table: Presentation round for all attendees to get to know each other
- 35' Interactive Session: Core of the session; online input gathering and discussion on success factors related to Industry-Academia Collaboration
- 10' Conclusions & Wrap-Up: Last words to finalize the session

The interactive part of the session was organized in Miro. There, the participants could find all proposed success factors structured per category and could choose to confirm them, discuss them, reject them or even propose new ones. An example of the outcome of such success factors discussion can be found in Figure 17.

Structure & Organisation

Figure 17 : Example of the result of a success factor discussion

The discussions were noted down by post-its on the Miro board so they could easily serve as input for the final success factors.

The four different sessions were held successfully, and in each session, constructive discussions were observed.

V. PRESENTATION OF RESULTS

The aim is, among other things, to highlight the most relevant findings on motivation, processes, and obstacles. The following section is analogous to the survey and interview divided into the same six sections. For each section, the IAC results obtained in the survey and interview are presented. However, special attention is given to the success factors, as these are an essential objective of this report. The factors for successful collaboration were validated and completed with the help of four focus groups (see section IV.4). Barriers that have arisen are also elaborated. By interviewing industry and academia separately, a separate analysis of the results is possible.

1. Participant Background

The first section provides insights into the background of the participants, as already explained in section IV.

As shown in Figure 18, nearly 68% of the 71 survey participants have experience with IAC. Of the 50 academic participants (30 researchers and 20 students), 76% have already participated in an industry-academia collaboration. Nearly half (10) of the 21 industry respondents have experience with IAC. Of the 23 respondents who have not yet participated in an IAC, 91% can definitely imagine participating. Motivating factors include insights into companies, getting to know the views of others, knowledge sharing, and innovation potential.

Experience in IAC

Figure 18 : Experience of the survey participants in IAC

All 23 interviewees have experience with IACs or are at least currently preparing for an IAC soon. Participants' areas of expertise are diverse. All industries are represented from chemicals, transportation, digitalization, and manufacturing to engineering. Figure 19 shows the participants of the survey and interviews respectively.

Figure 19 : Participants for each group

2. Collaboration Background

This section provides background information on the IACs that survey and interview participants were involved in to provide information on motivation, project management, team composition, and funding.

The goal of the IACs and the motivation for participation vary from project to project. In both the survey and interview, creating an innovative product, developing new ideas, developing a new process, and problem-solving were the most frequently cited goals. Industry representatives identified new ideas and products, as well as outside perspectives and input, as motivations for IACs. Researchers' incentives are expressed in terms of insights into the industry and exploring and developing new things. Hands-on experience and expanding what they learned, knowledge, and new experiences were the most important motivators for students (cf. Figure 20).

Figure 20 : Motivation for IACs

As shown in Figure 22, most projects were initiated through liaison between industry and university partners. Only a few originated in the context of tenders or EU projects. In most cases, project leadership was in the hands of the researcher (50%), followed by industry (38%). In other cases (10 %), the project leadership was in the hands of a company and a university, or it was unclear. Only in one project (2%) the lead was in the hands of the students (cf. Figure 21).

Figure 21 : Survey results on project leadership during IAC

Students were involved in 54% of the projects, while researchers were in 85%. Since this report is intended to provide insight into IACs, at least one partner from the industry should also be involved.

However, in 4% no industry partner was mentioned. Possible explanations could be a misunderstanding of our definition of IAC or a mistake in selection. The collaborations mentioned in the interviews consistently involved partners from industry and academia.

In almost all collaborations, the group size was less than ten people. The percentage of partners from industry and academia on the team was project specific. In one IAC, the complete project team consisted of 45 participants. In this case the participants were divided into small groups of no more than ten participants.

Figure 22 : Survey results on project initiators for IAC

As shown in Figure 23, the project duration was also very individual. Most collaborations lasted between one and six months (38 %). 50% of the IACs had a duration of less than one year. But there were also IACs that lasted three to five years (21%). The results of the survey are consistent with the findings from the interviews.

Figure 23 : Survey results on project duration

In most collaborations, industry, government, or the EU have covered the costs incurred, academia was only mentioned once. As shown in Figure 24, the cost of the IACs was more than €100,000 in 60% of the cases and more than €500,000 in 33%. One interviewee from the industry mentioned that the additional costs for workshops, company visits, and travel were about as high as the project itself.

Figure 24 : Survey results on project budget for IAC

3. Collaboration Procedure

This section aims to get insights into the background of the collaboration, knowledge about the individual contributions of the participants and the frequency of meetings is also relevant.

The survey results show that all participants contributed to the success of the collaboration in different ways. Industry partners primarily provided input on the project goal and industry needs, as well as relevant information, data, and knowledge. Researchers mainly contributed expertise, a methodological approach, and the innovation process. Workforce, creative ideas, and knowledge were the most frequently cited factors contributed by students. No other partners besides industry, researchers, and students were involved in the collaboration.

The frequency of meetings is as individual as the project itself (cf. Figure 25). In most IACs, they occurred weekly (38%) or at least biweekly (17%). In some projects, meetings even took place daily or twice a week. In one project, exchanges occurred only once every four months.

The results of the interviews underscore the survey results already presented. Again, it was noted that all project participants were involved in and contributed to the solution of the project. The importance of regular meetings was also mentioned.

Figure 25 : Survey results on meeting frequency in IAC

4. Success Factors and Barriers

Since this report aims to address the success factors of an IAC, this section presents the factors that emerged from the interviews and surveys. Four focus groups helped to validate the 51 success factors and narrowed them down to 22. In addition, the 21 barriers encountered and the solutions to overcome them are presented. The findings on barriers are not presented in as much detail in this report as the success factors. Nevertheless, they

were helpful in the validation and can contribute to the further course of the project to avoid known barriers on the platform and in the method.

The interview asked specifically for success factors and barriers in IACs and therefore the negotiation of success factors will not be barriers to collaboration and vice versa.

4.1. Identified Success Factors

As part of the survey, participants could tick the success factors they have experienced from 13 given factors. The factors given are taken from the results of the template (see section IV.1) and the desktop research (see section II.). The Figure 26 shows the factors, with their size and thickness depending on how many times they were mentioned. The top three factors for the academic group were *access to knowledge and information* (87%), *communication* (79%), and *commitment from all stakeholders* (74%). The most relevant factors for the industry group were *access to knowledge and information* (90%), *communication* (70%), and *external expertise* (70%). Other factors cited were *access to young talent* and *diverse teams with different experiences*, and *previous experience with IAC*.

Figure 26 : Survey results on success factors in IACs

The success factors identified in the interviews were categorized into five groups: good communication and feedback, information and (technical) support, motivation and commitment, people and team, and structure and organization.

Good communication and feedback

Success factors in this category include *quick responses*, *eye-to-eye conversations*, *standardized communication*, and *good external and internal communication*. Fast and

standardized feedback and implementation of the feedback received were also factors mentioned in the interviews.

Quick responses, good internal communication, and quick feedback are success factors that were also highlighted as essential success factors by all three focus groups that discussed this section. Two of the three focus groups confirmed that *good external communication, responding to feedback received, and not taking feedback personally* were among the success factors. The third group did not necessarily see these factors as relevant for IACs and, in some cases, too specific. Factor *discussion at eye level* was viewed differently by the focus groups. One group saw this as a success factor, while the other two think that it is not. The South-Eastern EU group also suggested a *clear understanding of needs and desires* as a success factor. *Continuous communication* via defined interfaces was also added.

Good communication and feedback

- *Quick response/reactions*
- *Good internal communication*
- *Fast feedback*

Figure 27 : Success factors confirmed by the focus groups for good communication and feedback

Information and (technical) support

Essential to a successful IAC is *quick input from all partners and sharing of all relevant information and knowledge*. In addition, *support in case of questions or problems* was also mentioned in the interviews as conducive to collaboration.

These factors were also confirmed by three of the four focus groups. Two groups confirm *support with problems and questions* as essential success factors. The third group also agreed on those factors but noted that these are quite similar. The success factors of *access to relevant data and sharing of knowledge* and to *sharing information* were confirmed by all focus groups. Since these factors were also considered similar, they have been grouped under the success factor "*secure access to data and information*". An important issue with this success factor is the barriers to sharing due to the non-disclosure agreement (NDA). Therefore, it should be determined at the beginning of the project which data and information the involved actors can and are allowed to exchange during the collaboration.

Information and (technical) support

- *Support with problems*
- *Support with questions*
- *Secure access to data and information*

Figure 28 : Success factors confirmed by the focus groups for information and (technical) support

Motivation and commitment

Many interviews identified *high motivation*, *high discipline*, and *strong commitment* as essential success factors for an IAC. And the three focus groups also underline their importance. *Working fast* is rated as a success factor needing discussion. The focus groups agreed that working fast is not always good or positive, but in some situations, it is necessary. The success factor of *high discipline* is seen controversially. One focus group agreed that it was a must, while another felt that it was too subjective and that delivering quality was more important. The success factor of *making all participants feel like they are part of the solution* should already be ingrained in the IAC and is considered as given. The focus groups did not suggest any additional success factors for this group.

Motivation and commitment

- *Strong commitment*
- *High motivation of all participants*

Figure 29 : Success factors confirmed by the focus groups for motivation and commitment

People and team

This group summarizes all success factors related to team dynamics and composition as well as information about the participants. These include *students' openness*, *diverse group composition*, or *methodologically and technically skilled individuals*.

The two focus groups that validated this category agreed that five success factors are essential to successful IACs. These include: *the presence of technically and methodologically trained people* and *all relevant competencies* in the project team. The *high reliability* of participants and *good team dynamics* round out this group. Other factors were rated as "nice to have" but not as an essential success factor on which the IAC depends. For example, *diverse team composition* is beneficial but not a requirement for IAC. The same is true for consideration of *cultural aspects*. *Student openness* and *clear responsibilities* are factors that were discarded because an IAC is a dynamic process that often leads to changes in responsibilities.

People and team

- *Availability of all relevant competencies*
- *Technically trained people*
- *Methodologically trained people*
- *High reliability*
- *Good team dynamics*

Figure 30 : Success factors confirmed by the focus groups for people and team

Structure and organisation

The structure and organisation category includes the most success factors because it is essential for an IAC to have unambiguous structures to be successful. The two focus groups that reviewed this category reduced the list from 19 to nine success factors on which they agreed. The other factors are still relevant for collaborations but not mandatory.

Clear project goals, a clear definition of tasks, and clear structures within the project are three essential success factors for collaborations, as is a *clear framework*. Other factors within this category include *efficient project management* and *efficient working*. One focus group noted that *efficient working* is a success factor not only for IACs but for anything. The factors *methodological support* and *tool support*, as well as *continuous documentation* complete this category. The statement that *tool support* and *continuous documentation* are neglected by most, but are helpful for transparency and communication within the project, underlines the importance of both factors. The *on-site collaboration* factor was deemed worthy of discussion as it depends on the frequency of meetings and the status of the project. In addition, *working remotely* has proven to be effective in recent years. *Sticking to agreements* and *clearly defined work packages* was also rated as worthy of discussion, as some flexibility in collaboration can be essential.

Structure and organisation

- *Clear project goals*
- *Clear task definition*
- *Clear structure of the project*
- *Clear framework/ processes*
- *Efficient project management*
- *Efficient working*
- *Methodological support*
- *Tool support*
- *Continuous documentation of the project*

Figure 31 : Success factors confirmed by the focus groups for structure and organisation

Overview of essential success factors

The chart in Figure 32 summarizes the 22 essential success factors for IACs identified in the interviews and confirmed in the four focus groups. Finally, it should be noted that the other success factors for internal communication mentioned in the interviews can also be important but are not among the top success factors. An overview of all identified success factors from the interviews can be found in ANNEX 1.

Figure 32 : Overview of all relevant success factors for IACs

4.2. Identified Barriers

The survey included 13 predefined obstacles that can occur during collaboration. The factors given are taken from the results of the template (see section IV.1) and the desktop research (see section II). Additional barriers could be added. All factors can be seen in the word cloud in Figure 33. The biggest barrier for both groups was *communication*. 45% of academics and 50% of industry representatives saw this during IAC. *Different priorities* regarding the project are also an obstacle mentioned quite frequently by both groups (academia: 45%, industry: 30%). The third commonly mentioned obstacle in the academia group is the *commitment* of all parties involved (45%). In the industry group, *access to knowledge and information* (30%) and *waiting times* (50%) were additional frequently mentioned obstacles. Other barriers cited were the *Covid-19 pandemic*, *financial instability*, and *implementation or reuse of results*.

Figure 33 : Survey results on barriers in IACs

The barriers to IACs mentioned in the interviews were divided into five categories. One barrier in the section on good communication and feedback was a *lack of communication*. The communication barriers occurred both between the different stakeholders and within their groups. *Different and incomplete information* was also frequently mentioned in the barriers section. In most cases, this could be attributed to an NDA issue.

One respondent cited *motivational differences* as a barrier they encountered during the IAC. This hindered and delayed their work and resulted in a heavier workload.

Difficulties in *agreeing on deadlines* within the project and with external experts were also obstacles experienced. Some projects were also hampered by *unclear and unrealistic goals* and *last-minute changes* to milestones and objectives. *Finding the right contact person* in the industry or at the university is often not easy and demotivating, as this process can be lengthy.

An overview of all identified barriers and factors from the interviews can be found in ANNEX 2.

5. Results

The survey asked participants to rate the outcome of the collaboration on a scale of 1 = goal not achieved to 5 = goal fully achieved. As the accompanying chart (Figure 35) shows, the outcome of IACs was consistently rated very highly in the surveys. Only one (2%) of the 48 participants with IAC experience rated the outcome as 1. The fact that 81% of the results were rated 4 or 5 confirms that the objectives of the IACs were largely achieved.

The responses from the interviews confirmed the results. The academics often rate the results as good but do not know if and how the obtained results are further used. Industry partners also mentioned that they do not know what happens to the results after the collaboration. Figure 34 shows an exemplary quote of an interviewee.

"[...] The prototypes developed during the collaboration later reached a 60% global market share as a finished product."

Figure 34 : Quote from academia interviewee A6

Industry interviewee I6 clearly emphasized that the goal of the collaboration was not a finished product but to gain other perspectives and new ideas. The results provide inputs for new ideas, which the company considers a great success. There were no statements that the participants were completely dissatisfied with the outcome of the IAC.

Figure 35 : Survey results on the ranking of the IACs

6. Conclusion – Thoughts of Participants

The conclusion section aims to identify information about participants' motivation for upcoming challenges and their thoughts about the platform.

Of the 48 survey participants with IAC experience, 47 (98%) would participate in an IAC again. The one participant who would not participate again indicated that the IAC was time-consuming, costly, and too stressful for little progress. Other participants expressed that they would attend another collaboration if the right conditions were met, concerning communication, feedback, or funding. Some mentioned that they have already participated in another IAC or plan to expand on the current one. Industry insights and new outside perspectives were identified as motivators for upcoming challenges.

Of the 19 companies surveyed that can imagine participating in an IAC again or for the first time, 89% can imagine offering their challenges to academia through a platform, and only 11% cannot. However, 100% of the companies surveyed would use the platform as a starting point for collaboration. Looking at all respondents who would like to collaborate again, 87% said they would use the platform. Some responses emphasized the need for such a platform, while others cited difficulties such as trust, security, or professionalism.

The results of the interviews underline that most respondents are open to new collaborations. Especially industry and researchers want to participate again in IACs or are currently planning to do so.

Opinions about the platform were more controversial. All views were represented by the statement that a great run is to be expected to scepticism and rejection. One point against the platform was the public disclosure of information about technical progress, even to potential competitors. The fact that the teams are made up of students and researchers from different universities and the strict requirement for a quota of women led to some

scepticism. One company values local partners highly and prefers local projects over international ones.

Many interviewees were not entirely opposed but still found it difficult to imagine the platform and how it would work. Therefore, it will be our task to clearly explain in our communication how the platform works. It is particularly important to ensure professionalism, trust, security, and protection from competitors, but also personal contact and good mapping.

VI. CONCLUSION

The final section of this report summarizes the findings obtained through desktop research, IAC best practices, interviews, and surveys. The goal of this report was to identify the success factors needed to create a methodology and platform to enable successful IACs. Impressions were also gathered on motivation, structures, and barriers.

The literature considered has already shown the relevance of collaborations between industry and universities. Several publications have already dealt with the success factors and barriers in such collaborations, with the insights mostly gained from personal experience or with the help of surveys or interviews. Communication, motivation, and trust were just some of the factors highlighted in terms of their importance for successful collaboration.

Section III presented the two best practices Agorize and Telanto. These are two internationally operating platforms that enable IAC. Both already have several years of experience and a large user base but differ partly in the services they offer. Agorize is an all-in-one solution that allows companies to post challenges of any kind for students to apply to. Telanto, on the other hand, provides a marketplace where both companies and universities can post tasks. The analysis showed that competitors in the market already offer good products. The presented platforms serve as a basis for the development of the methodology and the platform within the INDUSAC project.

An interview guide and survey were developed using the methods detailed in Section IV. These included topics on motivation, communication, working methods, barriers, and success factors. With the help of all partners, eleven interviews were conducted for the academic group and twelve interviews for the industry group. The structure of the survey was based on the interviews and provided additional insights and motivating factors for the IACs. A detailed analysis of all responses was provided in Section V. The 71 surveys provided quantitative statements for each section that were corroborated and supported by the interviews. The list of identified success factors was validated by focus groups in four different European regions. Once the factors were validated, a list of key success factors was developed for the IAC. It should be noted, however, that even factors not selected can make an important contribution to IACs, as each collaboration is different.

This report has provided 22 success factors for IAC, which are clustered into five groups: good communication and feedback, information and (technical) support, motivation and commitment, people and team, and structure and organization. The report also gained insights into the background, process, and financing of collaborations, as well as initial opinions on an IAC platform. The findings and results of this report provide an important foundation for the next steps in the INDUSAC project. In particular, the success factors will help as input factors in the creation of the methodology and platform.

VII. LIST OF REFERENCES

- Agorize. (2022a). Accelerate innovation management with Agorize software. <https://get.agorize.com/en/>
- Agorize. (2022b). Agorize. <https://www.agorize.com/de/challenges?group=2>
- Cirella, S., & Murphy, S. (2022). Exploring intermediary practices of collaboration in university–industry innovation: A practice theory approach. *Creativity and Innovation Management*, 31(2), 358–375. <https://doi.org/10.1111/caim.12491>
- Ehrismann, D., & Patel, D. (2015). University - industry collaborations: Models, drivers and cultures. *Swiss Medical Weekly*, 145, w14086. <https://doi.org/10.4414/smw.2015.14086>
- Fernandes, G., O’Sullivan, D., & Ferreira, L. M. D. (2022). Addressing the Challenges to Successfully Manage University-Industry R&D Collaborations. *Procedia Computer Science*, 196, 724–731. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2021.12.069>
- Garnweidner-Holme, L., Lieberg, H. S., Irgens-Jensen, H., & Telle-Hansen, V. H. (2021). Facilitators of and barriers to collaboration between universities and the food industry in nutrition research: A qualitative study. *Food & Nutrition Research*, 65. <https://doi.org/10.29219/fnr.v65.7874>
- Garousi, V., Eskandar, M. M., & Herkiloğlu, K. (2017). Industry–academia collaborations in software testing: experience and success stories from Canada and Turkey. *Software Quality Journal*, 25(4), 1091–1143. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11219-016-9319-5>
- Garousi, V., Pfahl, D., Fernandes, J. M., Felderer, M., Mäntylä, M. V., Shepherd, D., Arcuri, A., Coşkunçay, A., & Tekinerdogan, B. (2019). Characterizing industry-academia collaborations in software engineering: evidence from 101 projects. *Empirical Software Engineering*, 24(4), 2540–2602. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10664-019-09711-y>
- Hanid, M., Mohamed, O., Othman, M., Danuri, M. S. M., Mei Ye, K., & Berawi, M. A. (2019). Critical Success Factors (CSFS) In University-Industry Collaboration (UIC) Projects in Research Universities. *International Journal of Technology*, 10(4), 667. <https://doi.org/10.14716/ijtech.v10i4.668>
- Kauppila, O., Mursula, A., Harkonen, J., & Kujala, J. (2015). Evaluating university–industry collaboration: the European Foundation of Quality Management excellence model-based evaluation of university–industry collaboration. *Tertiary Education and Management*, 21(3), 229–244. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13583883.2015.1045550>
- Kleiner-Schaefer, T., & Schaefer, K. J. (2022). Barriers to university–industry collaboration in an emerging market: Firm-level evidence from Turkey. *The Journal of Technology Transfer*, 47(3), 872–905. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10961-022-09919-z>

Marijan, D., & Gotlieb, A. (2021). Industry-Academia research collaboration in software engineering: The Certus model. *Information and Software Technology*, 132, 106473. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.infsof.2020.106473>

Polese, F., Ciasullo, M. V., & Montera, R. (2021). Value co-creation in university-industry collaboration. An exploratory analysis in digital research projects. *Sinergie Italian Journal of Management*, 39(2), 117–134. <https://doi.org/10.7433/s115.2021.07>

Salimi, N., Bekkers, R., & Frenken, K. (2016). Success factors in university–industry PhD projects. *Science and Public Policy*, scv076. <https://doi.org/10.1093/scipol/scv076>

Serbezo, A., Rhinehart, R. R., Goupil, P., & Anisi, D. A. (2022). Academic-Practice Collaborations in Automation and Control: Keys for Success. *IFAC-PapersOnLine*, 55(17), 308–313. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ifacol.2022.09.297>

Steinmo, M., & Rasmussen, E. (2018). The interplay of cognitive and relational social capital dimensions in university-industry collaboration: Overcoming the experience barrier. *Research Policy*, 47(10), 1964–1974. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2018.07.004>

Telanto. (2022). TELANTO Global Academic Business Network. <https://telanto.com/about/vision>

VIII. ANNEXES

ANNEX 1 : Long list of success factors identified in the interviews.....	50
ANNEX 2 : Long list of barriers identified in the interviews.....	52

ANNEX 1 : Long list of success factors identified in the interviews

Success Factors

Good Communication & Feedback	
Success Factor	Explanation
quick response/reactions	
discussion at eye-level	
standardized communication structure	regular meetings, ping pong communication
good internal communication	communication within the group
good external communication	communication with the partners
fast feedback	
standardized feedback culture	continuous feedback, giving and taking feedback regularly
realization of received feedback	
not taking feedback personally	
Information & Support	
Success Factor	Explanation
fast input from the partners	
sharing all relevant information	
sharing/transferring knowledge	e.g. with workshops
access to relevant data	
support with problems	
support with questions	
Motivation & Commitment	
Success Factor	Explanation
high motivation of all participants	
high discipline	
fast working	fast first ideas, fast development of solutions, fast scheduling of appointments, etc.
strong commitment	
creating a useable solution	
giving all participants the feeling that they were part of the solution	

Figure 36 : Long list of success factors identified in the interviews (1/2)

People & Team	
Success Factor	Explanation
Availability of all relevant competencies	
professional background of participants	
technically trained people	
methodically trained people	
clear responsibility	
high reliability	
good team dynamics	
diverse group composition	mixed teams in terms of gender, expertise, and professional
consideration of cultural aspects	e.g. siesta
strengthening/supporting team building	
open mind of the students	
speaking the same language	in terms of comprehension, project goal, etc.
freedom in solving the task	in the way they want to achieve the project goal
trust in all participants	
trust in the project	
Structure & Organization	
Success Factor	Explanation
including view from the outside	
incorporate research view	
clear project goals	
well-defined work packages	
clear task definition	
clear structure of the project	
clear work division	
sticking to agreements and arrangements	
clear framework/processes	
efficient project management	
efficient working	
methodological support	
tool support	e.g. Teams, Miro, Google Drive etc.
continuous documentation of the project	
having a project manager	mediate between industry, students, and researchers
working together on-site	being physical present
high level of creativity	creative people, creative ideas, innovative creativity
regulated funding	
short lead time in planning the project	

Figure 37 : Long list of success factors identified in the interviews (2/2)

ANNEX 2 : Long list of barriers identified in the interviews

Barriers

Good Communication & Feedback	
Barrier	Explanation
lack of communication	
late responses	
language barriers	
Information & (Technical) Support	
Barrier	Explanation
different information	
incomplete information	
problems with the use of the platform	
dysfunctional IT access	
Motivation & Commitment	
Barrier	Explanation
differences in motivation	
Structure & Organization	
Barrier	Explanation
effortful scheduling of appointments with industry, students, and researchers	
effortful scheduling of appointments with experts outside the project	
unclear definition of the project goal	
unrealistic subgoals	
difficult collaboration procedure	
difficulties in finding the right contact person from the university	
short-term changes in milestones	
short-term changes in objectives	
physical distance	some topics are better discussed in person
part of the team working on-site and some remote	remote workers have only done the most necessary, missing motivation of the remote workers
unequal distribution of tasks	
distrust of the employees of the company	
contractual matters	NDA creation is sometimes lengthy

Figure 38 : Long list of identified barriers in the interviews

IX. LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1 : Structure of the baseline report.....	8
Figure 2 : Used search string for the literature review	9
Figure 3 : Number of publications per year found based on the search string	10
Figure 4 : Agorize - list of open challenges (Agorize, 2022b).....	13
Figure 5 : Agorize - full information about the challenge (Agorize, 2022b).....	14
Figure 6 : Agorize - company monitoring dashboard (Agorize, 2022a).....	15
Figure 7 : Telanto - challenge building (Telanto, 2022)	17
Figure 8 : Telanto - collaboration space (Telanto, 2022).....	18
Figure 9 : Advantages of cascade funding.....	20
Figure 10 : Challenges of cascade funding.....	21
Figure 11 : Overview of the methodology	22
Figure 12 : Template.....	23
Figure 13 : Interview structure.....	25
Figure 14 : Interview guide	26
Figure 15 : Conducting and evaluating the interviews	29
Figure 16 : Survey content.....	30
Figure 17 : Example of the result of a success factor discussion	32
Figure 18 : Experience of the survey participants in IAC.....	33
Figure 19 : Participants for each group.....	34
Figure 20 : Motivation for IACs.....	34
Figure 21 : Survey results on project leadership during IAC	35
Figure 22 : Survey results on project initiators for IAC.....	35
Figure 23 : Survey results on project duration.....	36
Figure 24 : Survey results on project budget for IAC.....	36
Figure 25 : Survey results on meeting frequency in IAC.....	37
Figure 26 : Survey results on success factors in IACs.....	38
Figure 27 : Success factors confirmed by the focus groups for good communication and feedback.....	39
Figure 28 : Success factors confirmed by the focus groups for information and (technical) support	39
Figure 29 : Success factors confirmed by the focus groups for motivation and commitment	40
Figure 30 : Success factors confirmed by the focus groups for people and team	40
Figure 31 : Success factors confirmed by the focus groups for structure and organisation..	41
Figure 32 : Overview of all relevant success factors for IACs.....	42
Figure 33 : Survey results on barriers in IACs	42
Figure 34 : Quote from academia interviewee A6.....	43
Figure 35 : Survey results on the ranking of the IACs	44
Figure 36 : Long list of success factors identified in the interviews (1/2).....	50

Figure 37 : Long list of success factors identified in the interviews (2/2).....	51
Figure 38 : Long list of identified barriers in the interviews.....	52

X. LIST OF TABLES

Table 1 : Overview of innovation platforms.....	19
Table 2 : Overview of conducted interviews.....	29

